

Relationship between Training Evaluation and Perceptions about XYZ Corporate University

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ABSTRACT: XYZ Corporate University plays a role in developing employee competencies, supporting XYZ Corporation performance, and filling competency gaps. One of the performance indicators is the Customer Satisfaction Index. The data shows that there is a gap, where the assessment from the participants states that the average rating has met the target, but the scores from superiors and business unit heads are still far from the target score. This brings forth the question of relationship between elements of training evaluation that influence perceptions towards XYZ Corporate University and how to improve it. Quantitative research methodology is used in this research with primary data gathered from employees of XYZ Corporation who filled out a set of questionnaires. For analysis technique, linear regression analysis is performed. From these results, XYZ Corporate University needs to prioritize Learners' Reaction and Changed Behavior after Learning, because increasing these two independent variables can affect the four dependent variables, namely positive perceptions of XYZ Corporate University. Of the five levels of training evaluation, Level 5, namely return on Training Investment, does not show a significant effect on perception, so further research is needed to examine its effect on training.

KEYWORDS: Corporate university, Customer satisfaction index, Perception, Training evaluation.

I. INTRODUCTION

This chapter introduces background, company profile and business issue that will be discussed throughout the research. Furthermore, this chapter presents research questions, objectives, scope, and limitations, as the fundamental part of the research.

A. Background

Nowadays, many companies in the world develop their own corporate universities. Referring to a study conducted by Baporikar, N. (2015), A corporate university is any educational entity that is a strategic tool designed to assist its parent organization in achieving its goals by conducting activities that foster individual and organizational learning and knowledge (Allen & Mark, 2002). In Indonesia, there are six types of corporate universities implementation with their respective characteristics through the process of cooperation between old and new companies with traditional universities through work laboratories that suit their needs so that Human Resource research and development activities can achieve the targets set (Suharto, 2017). According to a study conducted by Prince, C. et. al (2001), corporate universities in the United State of America almost reach the number of 1.800 (Bradshaw, 2000) and their growth becomes the fastest in the higher education category (Hoare, 1999). For example, the corporate university owned by Apple, Inc. in Cupertino, California, was initially designed in 2008 to instill Apple business culture and provide education regarding the history of the growth of Apple's business (Burrows, 2014). In Indonesia, the concept of corporate university was rising in popularity around the mid-2000s, when it was adopted by banking circles such as Citibank Indonesia and BUMN, consisting of Telkom, PLN and Pertamina as the early adopters (Sugiarsono et. al, 2017). This move is being followed by many other companies, until recently corporate universities are also adopted by private and government sectors. With the growing development of other corporate universities offering similar services and the fact that XYZ Corporate University has been established for more than 20 years, it is important to study whether XYZ Corporate University is still relevant to support organizational goals of XYZ Corporation in the eyes of stakeholders.

B. Company Profile

XYZ Corporate University officially established in 2012, however, the history of the organization had been long before that, where it began in 1960 as an Education Institute, which provided various technical training to employees. Moreover, it was developed as a vehicle for improving the quality of the company's human resources to become the Training Division in 1994. During this year,

Training Division collaborated on training with several international companies such as AT&T from the United States, PTT from the Netherlands, and JICA from Japan. In 2019, XYZ Corporate University managed to carve its name as a world-class institution as evidenced by Global Council of Corporate University Award. From the perspective of the Organization Structure, the Senior General Manager of XYZ Corporate University reports to the Chief of Human Capital Officer of XYZ Corporation. Referring to the Regulations of the Director of Human Capital Management in 2020, reporting to the Senior General Manager are Learning Diagnostic Squads, each is led by a Principal Learning Analyst, who are responsible to assist digital schools in capturing the solution needs required by users and reviewing the results of preparing learning materials and/or learning pathways, according to their job position at Customer Facing Unit and Functional Unit, consisting of Digital & Technology, Customer Retail Customer Corporate, and Leadership and Business Enabler. In addition, there are six schools of digital, each is led by a Senior Manager, which are responsible for the competency development, with designing and developing learning patterns according to the needs of the XYZ group business units grouped according to the type of CFU/FU, consisting of School of Digital Connectivity, School of Digital Leadership & Transformation, School of Digital Go To Market, School of Digital Enabler, School of Telecommunication & Media, and School of Digital Platform & Digital Services. Furthermore, XYZ Corporate University is also responsible for delivery and operation of training for the employees, including the learning facilities, administration processes, and the training activities itself. Therefore, XYZ Corporate University supports the company's mission by implementing programs to improve individual and organizational learning abilities in order to establish the center of excellence for XYZ Corporation. The roles of XYZ Corporate University are as follows: develop employee competence, support company performance, and fill competency gaps.

C. Business Issue

In carrying out its role, XYZ Corporate University has Key Performance Indicators which are manifested in Objectives & Key Results, one of which is the Customer Satisfaction Index (CSI) with the target of 85 in 2022. CSI measures the satisfaction of stakeholders from XYZ Corporate University, consisting of training participants, direct supervisors, and heads of business units.

Figure I.1 Customer satisfaction index of XYZ Corporate University in 2018-2021

Source: XYZ Corporate University report 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021

The bar chart shows the CSI from six categories from 2018 to 2021 (based on CSI Reports 2018, 2019, 2020, and 2021). The training participants are divided into three categories: functional, certification, and leadership training, with a note that certification training only being measured starting from 2020. The respondents for each training could be overlapped because it is possible for an employee to receive both functional and leadership training. For the leaders, there are direct supervisors divided into supervisors of functional and leadership training participants, and there is an additional survey introduced in 2020 to measure the satisfaction of the Head of Business Units.

Overall, the satisfaction of participants is rising over the period, except for leadership training that experienced a slight downward trend in 2019 to 2020, but peaked in 2021 with 85.76, being the only category that surpassed the score of 85. While none of the participants' satisfaction scored below 83 in 2021, the leaders' satisfaction scores were lower and barely touched 80 with the lowest point of 78.69 from heads of business units.

Customer Satisfaction Index is divided into three categories. The first category is 0-70 as below average, followed by 70-80 as average, and finally 80-100 as above average. If the CSI of XYZ Corporate University is below 70, it would be considered that XYZ Corporate University fails to deliver service to its customers hence will lower the achievement of performance indicator. The target set on 85, slightly above the minimum score 80 to be categorized as above average, is to challenge XYZ Corporate University ability to perform its task in providing training for employees.

From this phenomenon, it appears that the satisfaction level between training participants and their leaders experienced a contrast. Participants were satisfied with XYZ Corporate University but on the other hand their leaders did not rate it the same way. Consequently, this gap shows the level of success of XYZ Corporate University in carrying out its role in the eyes of stakeholders. Participants are the stakeholders who experienced training from XYZ Corporate University whereas their leaders are the ones who should be benefited from their subordinate's gaining knowledge, skill, and attitude needed to contribute to the business units.

D. Research Question and Research Objective

1) Research Question

- a) Is there any relationship between training evaluation and perceptions of XYZ Corporate University?
- b) What are the elements of training evaluation that influence perceptions of XYZ Corporate University?
- c) What recommendations can be proposed to improve the training from XYZ Corporate University?

2) Research Objective

This paper aims to find the relationship between training with perceptions of XYZ Corporate University. Knowing this connection would help to understand in which area XYZ Corporate University should improve to fulfill the expectation of training participant.

E. Research Scope and Limitation

The subject of this research consists of the employees of XYZ Corporation, not subsidiary entities, who receive training from XYZ Corporate University. The study conducted in this research is about perceptions of XYZ Corporate University, it is not assessing XYZ Corporate University as an institution.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In this subchapter, there are two aspects that would be covered which are training evaluation and training perception.

A. Training Evaluation

The first aspect that will be presented is Training Evaluation, which consists of two models namely Kirkpatrick Model and Phillips Model.

1) Kirkpatrick Model

A study conducted by Niemann, L., & Thielsch, M. T. in 2020 stated that according to Blau et al. (2012) the four-level model by Kirkpatrick is widely used in the context of evaluating training programs. In 1959, Dr. Donald Kirkpatrick first published four levels that need to be measured in training evaluation, which consists of Reaction, Learning, Behavior, and Results. This model is a tool for evaluating and analyzing the results of educational, training and learning programs. The explanation for the Four Levels would be as follows.

Firstly, in Level 1: Reaction, the explanation would be to what degree participants react favorably to the learning event. Secondly, in Level 2: Learning shows to what degree participants acquire the intended knowledge, skills and attitudes based on their participation in the learning event. The third level, Behavior, presents the evaluation of to what degree participants apply what they learned during training when they are back on the job. Finally, the fourth level is Results, which illustrates to what degree targeted outcomes occur, as a result of learning event(s) and subsequent reinforcement.

Furthermore, a study conducted by Andriushchenko et. al in 2022 explained that the level 4 of Kirkpatrick's Model, or simply known as result of training program, can be assessed using the tools such as perception of the effect of training of the participant by his leader, customer satisfaction, partners, business results (profit growth, sales, productivity, cost reduction), the perception of the effect on the business of the participant, the measurement of performance indicators of the participant, indicators of turnover and progress and ROI.

2) Jack Phillips Model

According to a study conducted by Tupamahu, S., & Soetjipto, B. W. (2005), some researchers also emphasize the importance of training evaluation based on financial calculations in order to provide real and firm information to companies regarding the contribution of training to company performance. Sandra Shelton and George Alliger (1993), Donna Goldwasser (2001), and Jack J. Phillips and Ron Drew Stone (2002) are some of the researchers who believe that companies must carefully calculate every dollar spent on training, and that this calculation must be in the context of business results and return on investment.

Referring to Phillips (2003), the Kirkpatrick Model should be expanded to include considerations for return on investment (ROI) of training programs. Therefore, the indicators become five levels as follows: Reaction, Learning, Behavior, Results, and Return of Training Investment. Return of investment is included to ensure that the investment in training has an impact on the business performance.

B. Training Perception

Referring to a study conducted by Sumanto (2014), it is stated that perceptions are formed based on data that we obtain from the environment that are absorbed by our senses, and some are obtained from processing our memories (reprocessed based on the experiences we have). As a result, perception emerges from someone after obtaining stimulus which leads to a thought process that develops into an opinion regarding an object. Furthermore, referring to Schiffman & Kanuk (2004), there are three components in shaping someone's perception, consist of cognitive, affective, and conative. From each component will emerge perception towards an object, with explanation as follows.

1) Trust

Trust is a positive expectation that another will not - through words, action, or decision - act opportunistically, where it is defined as the belief in the integrity, character, and ability of a leader (Stephen P. Robbins et.al, 2011). This is a positive perception emerging from cognitive components. Cognitive composed on knowledge basis or information that a person has about the object of his attitude, resulting certain beliefs regarding the object. The emerging perception is that the training participants believe that the training they receive is successful to boost their performance.

2) Competence

According to a study conducted by Jayakumar et.al in 2014, employee perception on training and development consists of three elements: status, effectiveness, and value. Effectiveness of the training program is based on the accuracy to find the needs of employees and the relevancy to the organization, which require competence to recognize the feedback regarding training and development in the organization. The perception of competence emerges from cognitive components resulting in certain beliefs, where in this case the training participants recognize that XYZ Corporate University is competent to deliver the training that they need to boost their performance.

3) Loyal

Training has to be in high standards which help employees to reach a high level. Furthermore, it could be presented in the commitment of managers and participation of individuals in capturing training and development opportunities (Jayakumar et.al, 2014). Loyalty established from conative component. Conative indicates a person's readiness to behave in relation to the object of his attitude. The conative component (behavioral component, or action component) is related to the tendency to act towards the object, where in this case translated as participants' willingness to attend training from XYZ Corporate University.

4) Pride

The component of perception is affective which relates to feelings of pleasure and displeasure. It is closely related to the cultural values or value system that someone cultivated through life hence it has the characteristic of evaluation. The perception resulting from this aspect would be emotional evaluation. One particular positive emotion that has a meaningful connection with the learning experience is that of pride (Ross, 2016).

III. METHODOLOGY

Following up the introduction from Chapter 1 and the literature review from Chapter 2, this third chapter explores the methodology of research that will be conducted to gather the necessary information. This chapter includes research design, data collection method, and data analysis method.

A. Research Design

Figure III.1 Research Design

The figure above depicts the research design to answer three research questions. The first question aims to find the relationship between training evaluation and perceptions of XYZ Corporate University while the second question seek for which elements of training evaluation influence participants' perceptions of the XYZ Corporate University training. To answer these two questions, quantitative research would be conducted to respondents. The items in the set of questionnaires are determined based on the literature study and will be checked for validity and reliability. The result of quantitative research would be analyzed to provide the information required to answer questions number 3 which is to determine the recommendations that can be proposed to improve the training from XYZ Corporate University in supporting company's performance.

B. Data Collection Method

The source of primary data is quantitative research to the employees of XYZ Corporation, not subsidiary entities, who receive training from XYZ Corporate University. Quantitative research is conducted to a number of samples that represents the whole population to gather the information regarding the set of questionnaires items. From the secondary data of company's Annual Reports Year 2021, the number of populations is 8.789 as the amount of all employees of XYZ Corporation. All employees of XYZ Corporation are required as the population because they receive training organized by XYZ Corporate University and contribute to the business performance, therefore they could give the necessary perspective. To determine the number of samples, this paper uses Slovin's formula with confident level 95%. The questionnaire was shared and filled out between 3 to 16 December 2022 with the results of 155 respondents with margin of error 8%.

C. Data Analysis Method

In analyzing the quantitative results, the validity and reliability of the questionnaire will be checked first. After that the profiles of respondents who filled out the survey were identified. Then a descriptive analysis was carried out to present an overview of the respondents' answers to each item and its variables. Finally, linear regression analysis will be carried out to see the extent to which the influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable, as shown in the following figure.

Figure III.2 Data Analysis Method

From the figure, there are five independent variables (X) that each linked into four dependent variables (Y). The independent variables (X) of Training Evaluation are Learners’ Reaction (X1), Learning Occurrence (X2), Changed Behavior after Learning (X3), Performance after Learning (X4), and Return of Training Investment (X5). The dependent variables (Y) of Perception are Trust (Y1), Competence (Y2), Loyal (Y3) and Pride (Y4). Multiple linear regression analysis, using an IBM SPS tool, of the five independent variables on the four dependent variables will be carried out to see the relationship and how far the independent variables influence the dependent variable.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter provides the results of research methodology explained in Chapter 3 which will be analyzed and discussed in detail to determine business solution. There are three subchapters, which consist of analysis, business solution, and implementation plan.

A. Analysis

This subchapter presents the results and discussion of the analysis of data obtained from 155 respondents which includes respondent profiles, descriptive analysis, linear regression analysis, and the discussion of overall results.

1) Respondent Profile

Based on the table below, the majority of respondents were female (52.9%), aged 25-30 years (59.4%), had work experience for 3-5 years (36.8%) and had an undergraduate degree (72.3%). There are total of 33 questions that have been checked on validity and reliability.

Table IV. 1 Respondent Profile

Respondent Profile	f	%
Gender		
Male	73	47.1%
Female	82	52.9%
Age		
< 25 years old	11	7.1%
25-30 years old	92	59.4%
31-35 years old	17	11.0%
36-40 years old	12	7.7%
41-50 years old	14	9.0%
> 50 years old	9	5.8%
Work Experience		
< 3 years	43	27.7%
3-5 years	57	36.8%
6-10 years	21	13.5%
11-15 years	10	6.5%
> 15 years	24	15.5%
Education		
D4	21	13.5%
S1 (Undergraduate)	112	72.3%
S2 (Graduate)	22	14.2%

2) Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive analysis aims to present an overview of respondents' answers to each item and variables. The statistics presented are mean or average values which are then confirmed with interpretation guidelines in the following six categories.

Table IV. 2 Interpretation

Interval Mean	Interpretation
1.00 - 1.83	Very Bad
1.84 - 2.67	Bad
2.68 - 3.50	Slightly Bad
3.51 - 4.33	Slightly Good
4.34 - 5.17	Good
5.18 - 6.00	Very Good

Table IV. 3 Recapitulation of Variable Training Evaluation

Variable Training Evaluation	Mean Score	Interpretation
X1. Learners' Reaction	4.97	Good
X2. Learning Occurrence	5.08	Good
X3. Changed Behavior After Learning	5.02	Good
X4. Performance After Learning	4.78	Good
X5. Return of Training Investment	4.55	Good
Variable Training Evaluation	4.88	Good

Figure IV.1 Recapitulation of Variable Training Evaluation

Based on the Table IV.3 and the Figure IV.1 above, the five aspects of the Training Evaluation Variable are in the Good category, with the highest score achieved by Learning Occurrence (5.08) and the lowest score achieved by Return of Training Investment (4.55).

Table IV. 4 Recapitulation of Variable Perception

Variable Perception	Mean Score	Interpretation
Y1. Trust	4.96	Good
Y2. Competence	4.88	Good
Y3. Loyal	5.17	Good
Y4. Pride	5.05	Good
Variable Perception	5.01	Good

Figure IV. 1 Recapitulation of Variable Perception

Based on the table and the bar chart above, the four aspects of the Perception Variable are in the Good category, with the highest score being Loyal (5.17) and the lowest score being Competency (4.88).

3) Linear Regression Analysis

The following table presents the results of multiple linear regression analysis of the five independent variables on the four dependent variables. This analysis is used to recognize how far the influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable. The results of the linear regression analysis are presented as follows.

Table IV. 5 Linear Regression Analysis of Y1 and Y2

Independent Variable	Y1. Trust			Y2. Competence		
	Regression Coefficient	Partial Hypothesis Test		Regression Coefficient	Partial Hypothesis Test	
		t-values	p-values		t-values	p-values
Partial Analysis						
Constant	-0.911			-0.498		
X1. Learners Reaction	0.141	2.772	0.006	0.106	2.326	0.021
X2. Learning Occurrence	0.031	0.597	0.552	0.159	3.390	0.001
X3. Changed Behavior After Learning	0.152	2.993	0.003	0.009	0.191	0.848
X4. Performance After Learning	0.060	1.150	0.252	0.100	2.127	0.035
X5. Return of Training Investment	0.057	1.505	0.135	0.044	1.292	0.198
Simultaneous Analysis						
Correlation Analysis (R)	0.830			0.849		
Analysis Coefficient Determination (R ²)	69.0%			72.2%		
Simultaneous Hypothesis Test						
F Stat	66.242			77.257		
p-value	0.000			0.000		

Based on the table above it can be explained as follows.

- a) Effect of Learners’ Reaction, Learning Occurrence, Changed Behavior After Learning, Performance After Learning dan Return of Training Investment on Trust (Y1).

The regression model result is:

$$Y1 = -0.911 + 0.141 X1 + 0.031 X2 + 0.152 X3 + 0.060 X4 + 0.057 X5$$

The simultaneous relationship between the five independent variables and the dependent variable is 0.830 (very strong relationship). The simultaneous effect of the five independent variables on the dependent variable is 69%. Based on the simultaneous hypothesis test (F test), the calculated F value is 66.242 with a probability value (opportunity) of 0.000. This shows that the five independent variables have a significant effect on Trust. Based on the partial hypothesis test (t test), of the five independent variables two independent variables were obtained which produced a p value <0.05, namely X1 and X3. Thus, X1 and X3 are stated to have a significant effect on Trust, while the other three independent variables (X2, X4 and X5) have no significant effect on Trust.

- b) Effect of Learners’ Reaction, Learning Occurrence, Changed Behavior After Learning, Performance After Learning dan Return of Training Investment on Competence (Y2).

The regression model result is:

$$Y2 = -0.498 + 0.106 X1 + 0.159 X2 + 0.009 X3 + 0.100 X4 + 0.044 X5$$

The simultaneous relationship between the five independent variables and the dependent variable is 0.849 (very strong relationship). The simultaneous effect of the five independent variables on the dependent variable is 72.2%. Based on simultaneous hypothesis testing (F test), the calculated F value is 77.257 with a probability value (opportunity) of 0.000. This shows that the five independent variables have a significant effect on competence. Based on the partial hypothesis test (t test), of the five independent variables, three independent variables were obtained which resulted in a value of p <0.05, namely X1, X2 and X4. Thus, X1, X2 and X4 are stated to have a significant effect on Competence, while the other two independent variables (X3 and X5) have no significant effect on Competence.

Table IV. 6 Linear Regression Analysis of Y3 and Y4

Independent Variable	Y3. Loyal			Y4. Pride		
	Regression Coefficient	Partial Hypothesis Test		Regression Coefficient	Partial Hypothesis Test	
		t-values	p-values		t-values	p-values
Partial Analysis						
Constant	1.800			-0.701		
X1. Learners Reaction	0.063	0.983	0.327	0.286	4.490	0.000
X2. Learning Occurrence	0.068	1.042	0.299	-0.134	-2.042	0.043
X3. Changed Behavior After Learning	0.147	2.310	0.022	0.178	2.795	0.006
X4. Performance After Learning	0.051	0.773	0.441	0.131	1.999	0.047
X5. Return of Training Investment	0.015	0.321	0.749	-0.023	-0.485	0.628
Simultaneous Analysis						
Correlation Analysis (R)	0.673			0.782		
Analysis Coefficient Determination (R2)	45.2%			61.1%		
Simultaneous Hypothesis Test						
F Stat	24.613			46.819		
p-value	0.000			0.000		

Based on the table above it can be explained as follows.

- a) Effect of Learners Reaction, Learning Occurrence, Changed Behavior After Learning, Performance After Learning and Return of Training Investment on Loyal (Y3).

The regression model result is:

$$Y3 = 1.800 + 0.063 X1 + 0.068 X2 + 0.147 X3 + 0.051 X4 + 0.015 X5$$

The simultaneous relationship between the five independent variables and the dependent variable is 0.673 (a strong relationship). The simultaneous effect of the five independent variables on the dependent variable is 45.2%. Based on simultaneous hypothesis testing (F test), the calculated F value is 24,613 with a probability value (opportunity) of 0.000 where the p value <0.05. This shows that the five independent variables have a significant influence on Loyal. Based on the partial hypothesis test (t test), of the five independent variables, two independent variables were obtained which resulted in a value of p <0.05, namely X3. Thus, X3 is stated to have a significant effect on loyalty, while the other four independent variables (X1, X2, X4 and X5) have no significant effect on loyalty.

- b) Effect of Learners' Reaction, Learning Occurrence, Changed Behavior After Learning, Performance After Learning and Return of Training Investment on Pride (Y4) The regression model result is:

$$Y4 = -0.701 + 0.286 X1 - 0.134 X2 + 0.178 X3 + 0.131 X4 - 0.023 X5$$

The simultaneous relationship between the five independent variables and the dependent variable is 0.782 (a strong relationship). The simultaneous effect of the five independent variables on the dependent variable is 61.1%. Based on the simultaneous hypothesis test (F test), the calculated F value is 46.819 with a probability value (opportunity) of 0.000. This shows that the five independent variables have a significant effect on Pride. Based on the partial hypothesis

test (t test), of the five independent variables one independent variable was obtained which resulted in a value of p <0.05, namely X1, X2, X3 and X4. Thus, X1, X2, X3 and X4 are stated to have a significant effect on Pride, while one other independent variable, namely X5, is stated to have no significant effect on Pride.

4) Discussion of Overall Results

Based on previous subchapters, the descriptive analysis of the survey shows that respondents scored both the Training Evaluation Variable and Perception Variable in the Good category. Furthermore, it is shown that the training evaluation scored good overall and each of the five aspects (Learners Reaction, Learning Occurrence, Changed Behavior After Learning, Performance After Learning, Return of Training Investment) was also fell into the good category. At the same time, the perception was also considered good by the respondents, as well as each of the four aspects namely Trust, Competence, Loyalty, and Pride.

On the regression analysis, there are four relationships for each dependent variable as follows:

- a) Learners Reaction, Learning Occurrence, Changed Behavior After Learning, Performance After Learning, Return of Training Investment has a simultaneous significant effect on Trust, with a simultaneous effect of 69%. But partially, only Learners Reaction and Changed Behavior After Learning have a significant effect on Trust, while the other three variables are stated to have no significant effect. Therefore, improving the quality of these two aspects would help to increase the trust of stakeholders towards XYZ Corporate University. XYZ Corporate University needs to ensure that learners enjoy the training and the training changed behavior
- b) Simultaneously, Learners Reaction, Learning Occurrence, Changed Behavior After Learning, Performance After Learning, Return of Training Investment has a significant effect on competent perception, with a simultaneous effect of 72.2%. But partially, only three variables, consisting of Learners Reaction, Learning Occurrence, and Performance After Learning, have a significant effect, while the other two variables are stated to have no significant effect. Therefore, improvement on these three aspects would help to increase the competence of XYZ Corporate University in the eyes of stakeholders.
- c) Learners Reaction, Learning Occurrence, Changed Behavior After Learning, Performance After Learning, Return of Training Investment has a simultaneous significant effect on Loyalty, with a simultaneous effect of 45.2%. But partially, only Changed Behavior After Learning has a significant effect on Loyalty, while the other four variables have no significant effect. Only improving this aspect would lead to increase in loyalty towards XYZ Corporate University programs, which shown in the willingness to attend training. However, it is also important to note that the simultaneous effect was 45.2% meaning that there is another factor outside Training Evaluation aspects that affect respondents to be loyal to XYZ Corporate University's programs.

- d) Simultaneously, Learners Reaction, Learning Occurrence, Changed Behavior After Learning, Performance After Learning, Return of Training Investment has a significant effect on Pride, with a simultaneous effect of 61.1%. However, partially, the four independent variables, namely Learners Reaction, Learning Occurrence, Changed Behavior After Learning, Performance After Learning, have a significant effect on Pride, while the variable that has no significant effect is Return on Training Investment. In addition, when looking into the detail, it turns out that in Level 2 (learning occurrence) there is a negative t-values with pride, which means that high learning occurrence would lower the pride towards XYZ Corporate University. Therefore, any adjustment on four aspects will affect the pride towards XYZ Corporate University.

B. Business Solution

Based on these results, there are business solutions that could be proposed to improve the training from XYZ Corporate University:

1. Learners enjoyed the training (Level 1 of Kirkpatrick Model) and the training changed behavior (Level 3 of Kirkpatrick Model) need to be improved first because these two aspects could affect four positive perceptions. Based on the survey, these two aspects fell into the Good category meaning that there is room for improvement to Very Good, where they could provide significant impact to the perception of XYZ Corporate University.
2. Level 1 can be improved by the training events delivery aspect to increase satisfaction with recommendations as follows:
 - a) Ensure that the material content match with the objective of the program.
 - b) Deliver training in more interesting ways, for example increase participants engagement by doing two-way communications instead of one-way by lecture.
 - c) Provide fasilitators who own the necessary knowledge and skill according to the program
 - d) Improve the accuracy between training and the competency needed.
3. Level 3 can be enhanced by providing training that motivates and inspires participants to implement changes. For instance, giving the reason why participants need to enroll to a certain training at the start of the first day of training.
4. Level 4 (performance) have positive relationship with perception of competence and pride of XYZ Corporate University; therefore, it will also be beneficial to improve this aspect by accommodate training programs that possess direct correlation, link and match with the target performace of the job.
5. In Level 2 (learning occurrence) there is a negative t-values with pride, which means that high learning occurrence would lower the pride towards XYZ Corporate University. On the other hand, the relationship is positive with competence, meaning that learning occurrence need to be higher to increase perception that XYZ Corporate University is competent in fulfilling its role, however it would lead to decrease in Pride. Therefore, further research should be conducted to study this phenomenon.
6. The variable of Return of Training Investment shows no significant effect with perception. However, based on the literature review in chapter 2, it appears that some researchers also emphasize the importance of training evaluation based on financial calculations in order to provide real and firm information to companies regarding the contribution of training to company performance (Tupamahu, S., & Soetjipto, B. W., 2005). Hence, there are two recommendations regarding this matter:
 - a) Return of Training Investment should be introduced in each training to ensure that participants aware that participating in training is an investment made by the company and leaders must also recognize that the training that their subordinates participate in has significant value that can be accounted in performance results.
 - b) XYZ Corporate University which exists as a vehicle to support the business of XYZ Corporation must pay attention to the Return of Training Investment aspect in addition to the other 4 aspects. In addition to identifying learning needs, it is also necessary to identify Return of Training Investment for each training conducted to employees to ensure that every dollar spent on training is calculated in the context of business results and return on investment.

C. Implementation Plan

Business solutions from previous sub chapter requires collaboration between units in XYZ Corporate University. The first step to take is getting buy in from Management. In order to obtain the approval, the Planning and Controlling Unit must be informed first

to ensure the alignment with Yearly Commitment. After that, if the Management approved the plan, there are two units that would need follow up, consists of Squad Learning Diagnostic (SLD) and Schools, because they are accountable and responsible for Learning Process in XYZ Corporate University. In addition, any adjustment in learning operations and delivery which manifest as Level 1 (Learners' Reaction) would impact the unit that responsible for learning operation, which is the unit of Learning, Research, and Innovation Fulfillment. Therefore, a socialization would be needed to be conducted.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

On this final segment, the final answer to the research questions is provided and concluded with a summary of recommendation. The conclusion follows up the findings in the previous chapter while the recommendation provides practical implication and future research suggestion.

A. Conclusion

From the findings in Chapter 4, it can be concluded that there is a relationship between training evaluation and the perception of XYZ Corporate University, both simultaneously and partially. There are five levels of training evaluation, consist of Learners' Reaction, Learning Occurrence, Changed Behavior after Learning, Performance after Learning, and Return of Training Investment, which simultaneously affect each of perception, consists of trust, competence, loyal, and pride. The partial analysis reveals that Level 1 (Learners' Reaction) alone influence the perception of trust, competence, and pride; while Level 3 (Changed Behavior after Learning) alone influence trust, loyalty, and pride. Therefore, focusing the effort on improving these two aspects would generate significant increase in the perception towards XYZ Corporate University.

B. Recommendation

Collaboration between Squad Learning Diagnostics and Schools at XYZ Corporate University to identify action plan that can be derived from this project is needed after getting buy-in from Management. The action plan can be combined with the Human Capital Development Plan and Yearly Commitments for employees and managers. This research focuses on the perception of training participants, therefore perception from internal employees of XYZ Corporate University itself could be investigated to explore the reflection towards training that is provided by XYZ Corporate University.

From the research results it is known that the variable of Return on Training Investment has no significant effect on perceptions about XYZ Corporate University, but respondents have rated this item in the good category. On the other hand, according to researchers, the return on training investment is important to calculate. Thus, a further study is necessary to find an accurate method of calculating the return on training investment to determine the quality of the training provided.

The result of the learning occurrence variable shows that the higher the value, the better the perception regarding XYZ Corporate University competence in carrying out their duties. However, the higher the learning occurrence, the lower the pride in XYZ Corporate University. Therefore, it is necessary to learn more about what kind of increase in learning occurrence that can escalate XYZ Corporate University competence without reducing the perception of pride in the training provided by XYZ Corporate University.

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